

INVESTIGATING 8TH GRADE STUDENTS' MEDIA LITERACY

Seilkhanova A.

*Master's student in the educational program "Training Foreign Language Teachers",
Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages, Kazakhstan*

Abstract

Media literacy is often understood as a basic skill, and it is gaining recognition as the most functional means to educational attainment and individual development. It not only sets a benchmark but also reveals students' strengths and weaknesses through performance measurement. This paper attempts to investigate 8th grade students' media literacy proficiency and necessary skills to interpret graph-based information using a performance band system. The study involved a total of 12 students of 8th grade in N 202 school-gymnasium. Descriptive quantitative research method was employed to define the students' current media literacy level and mandatory skills to cope with different graphics-based text materials. The study measured the students' media literacy level based on a proficiency scale spanning on five-band levels. The findings of the present study revealed that the majority of the students scored Band 3, where they demonstrated a moderate understanding of texts and were able to integrate some parts of texts to infer meaning. The study provides valuable insights to policymakers, educationists, employers in making data - driven decisions to improve educational outcomes. It also attempts to shed some light on the investigation of students' current media literacy level and necessary skills in reading sections of PISA.

Keywords: media literacy; PISA; infographics; cognitive skills.

Introduction

The main task of modern media is to provide citizens with information about what is happening in the country, generally, in the whole world where it is still not enough for a person to be able to read, count and write correctly (Wilson & Dornan, n.d.). Information is received through various media and various information channels. Majority of the students do not have the ability to find information, to use it from a useful angle, to think critically. To do this, you need to firmly master the competence called media and information literacy which is a set of skills acquired as a result of the process of personal development in order to form a culture of communication with the media (media), creative, communicative abilities, critical thinking, skills of full perception, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of media texts, teaching various forms of self-expression with the help of media technology (Bykov & Medvedeva, n.d.).

In this regard, Kazakhstan participates in the international PISA study to determine the level of educational achievements of students of the country (Massyrov et al., 2015). The main task of the international PISA study is to analyze the clear results obtained through objective measurements based on research tools that characterize global priorities in the field of Education (OECD, 2019). Generally, 79% of test tasks are presented in the form of a chart, that is, in the form of numbers and data that clearly describe the problem, and 21% are questions with a choice of answers (Higgins, 2019). In addition, the test participants will answer the questionnaire questions to get additional information about their attitude to global problems in the world (ecology, world culture, attitude to representatives of other nationalities, ethnicities, demography and migration) (Mihăilescu & Sarivan, 2020) The status of the study is also evidenced by the increase in the number of participating countries at each stage. Our country has experience in participating in 4 cycles of PISA research (2009, 2012, 2015, 2018). Based on the results

obtained, it contributed to the improvement of educational programs and the introduction of new teaching technologies (Hu & Yu, 2021).

However, in the PISA ranking of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) on the quality of school education for 2012, 2015 and 2018, we can see a decrease in the indicator of Kazakhstan. Kazakhstan is not among the fifty countries that are ahead of others. One of the main reasons for this is that 30% of the tasks in the test structure are presented in infographic format (Hopfenbeck et al., 2018). Therefore, the relevance of the research paper is that students still have insufficient ability to interpret text and graphic (table, diagram, figure, symbols) information, describe the process presented in the form of graphic text (conditional sign, drawing, diagram), while maintaining the structure of the text (introduction, section, general information, detailed information) (Mendizábal et al., 2017).

Therefore, the present study aims to investigate thoroughly the 8th grade students' current media literacy level and skills to interpret infographics-based tasks in PISA. Specifically, this study addresses the following research questions:

1. What level of media literacy are the 8th grade students on?
2. What skills are needed to form the 8th grade students' media literacy?

Literature review

Media Literacy

Currently changes are taking place in the education system providing all areas of our life. According to some studies, enhancing the foreign media literacy of students in order to get higher results in international PISA testing is one of the main issues in the education field of Kazakhstan (Koltay, 2011). In connection with the globalization of education and the expansion of the country's cultural, economic and political borders and entry into the international educational space, the education of a competitive, educated nation, ready for a foreign language, in particular English, intercultural

professional communication, able to think analytically, get out of any situation in an optimal way, requires training from the walls of school (Hipkins, 2019). Awareness of the main features of the teaching of the academic discipline "foreign language" in the main secondary school is the main factor in increasing the media literacy of students, as well as contributing to the development of motivation and interest of students in the process of teaching a foreign language (Aydın & Özgeldi, 2019).

Previous studies indicated that media literacy is "the ability of a person to interact with the external environment and to adapt and work in it as quickly as possible" (Hossein Kaveh et al., 2015). Whereas the notion of media literacy has been discussed by a great number of authors in literature indicating that it is the level of knowledge, skills that ensure the normal functioning of a person in a system of social relations, which is considered the least necessary for the realization of a person's life in a particular cultural environment (Bykov & Medvedeva, n.d.). If we generalize these statements that have been mentioned above, media literacy is the ability to read and understand, compose texts, as well as perform simple mathematical actions.

They must also be able to find information, use it usefully, and think critically and creatively. To do this, it is necessary to firmly master the so-called media information literacy skills (Nurgiyantoro et al., 2020). Media literacy is a way to make full use of different types of media (Silverblatt, 2018).

Media literacy is a set of skills that allow a person to access media, how to lease media content, create new video information links, and think of existing video content (Wilson & Dornan, n.d.). Media literate people are often able to understand the message of newspapers, magazines, books, radio, television, billboards, video and computer games, music, the internet, social media and all other media forms, as well as independently create media messages (Suwana & Lily, 2017).

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, president of the Russian Association of media pedagogy Fedorov (2020) defines "media education" as "the process of personal development through media and through material."

Formation of a culture of communication with the media, creative, communicative abilities, critical thinking, skills of full perception, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of media texts, training in various forms of self-expression with the help of Media Technology (Fedorov & Mikhaleva, 2020)

The goal of media education, as Fedorov (2020) considers, is the formation of Media Culture, the development of "critical thinking" and the self-expression of people through the means of mass communication.

Thus, we are convinced that foreign media literacy is the skills acquired as a result of the process of personal development in order to form a culture of communication with the media (media), creative, communicative abilities, critical thinking, skills of full perception, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of media texts, training various forms of self-expression with the help of media technology.

Therefore, the analysis of the content of the concept of "media literacy" allows us to conclude that a high level of media literacy, the formation of personal skills, such as communication and reflective skills, text search, conclusion, implies a high degree of further use and assimilation of information from the text. In the social aspect, media literacy is an indicator of the level of knowledge and the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in standard and non-standard situations (Bruinenberg et al., 2021).

Infographics

The majority of previous research has applied the notion of infographics as a promising, powerful and effective tool for presenting data, explaining concepts, simplifying presentations, comparing relationships, highlighting trends, and presenting key information (Dunlap & Lowenthal, 2016). Some authors have also suggested that they adhere to a multi-sensory and multimodal approach, that is, text and visual effects (Ozdamli & Ozdal, 2018). These considerations clarify that infographics help convey information more effectively in a concise form. For example, recent research suggests that they are a tool for turning important points of complex information into a visual story (Bicen & Beheshti, 2022). Using attractive images, infographics make it easier to understand abstract ideas, which is why it is popular both in teaching and in other areas (Alrwele, 2017). It provides expanded cooperation, understanding and coherence, as well as interaction and involvement of students in the educational and cognitive process with systematic and planned use. This explains the complex process in a simple and easy way. It is also useful when comparing and analyzing different concepts. In addition, it helps to present the reports, data and results of any project or study in the form of a resume (Bystrova, 2020). Thus, infographics can be an important tool to facilitate teaching and learning; research and advocacy work related to the presentation, helping to understand and analyze them (Provvidenza et al., 2019).

It can convey the idea that readers and viewers will take away. Infographics attract more attention if they are attractive and have a balanced combination of relevant colors, visual effects, graphic design, short texts and diagrams (Chokshi, 2021).

According to some studies, the infographic has several components such as title, source, author credits, brief text, and a body that includes graphic elements. The title can be accompanied by a subtitle if it is necessary. And a short text gives an explanation and its criteria called labels that contain an explanation of the entire infographic, detailed information about the added elements, data appearance, and information about the infographic designer (Yarbrough, 2019).

However, some researchers have proposed three components inasmuch as visual elements (color, graphics, icons, maps, symbols, etc.), content elements (based on facts, links, statistics, texts, etc.) and academic elements (related to conclusions, messages, etc.) (Naparın & Binti Saad, 2017).

Depending on the complexity, infographics are divided into several categories: those that graphically

represent statistical information (bars, coordinate systems), maps (closely related to geographic information), boards (rows and columns built on the basis of colors and pictograms), diagrammatic (used to indicate the articulation of hierarchies and processes, the operation of certain systems), video and interactive (Damyanov & Tsankov, 2018).

A recent study by some investigators concluded that describing the potential of visual aids, the visual systems section notes that visual data is processed by the brain 60,000 times faster than text, and visual aids in the classroom improve reading by up to 400 percent. The use and effectiveness of infographics is well proven. It improves the cognitive abilities of the visual system of students by using graphics to improve their ability to see patterns and trends (Makulin & Korzina, 2020).

Engaging students through infographics gives great results and increases academic performance. This encourages students to read facts, interpret data, and draw conclusions easily and comprehensively. Instead of conveying ideas through the chalk and conversational method, it encourages students to take notes in a consistent manner (Alyahya, 2019). It serves as a promising teaching tool in the teaching and learning process. Its potential advantages include:

1. improved interpretation of information,
2. concepts and ideas,
3. improve the ability to understand complex information and
4. information can be classified as improving memory and storage (Yuan et al., 2022).

Some authors have also considered several infographic tools available on the internet such as Canva (free graphic design platform used to create invitation cards, Instagram posts and business cards), Venngage (online application for infographics, reports and data visualization), Piktochart (for creating slides, presentations, posters and reports), Visme (for infographics, videos or presentations on the internet), Visualizeme (for LinkedIn users), Snappa (for social media, media ads, blog posts)(Jones et al., 2019).

Researchers presented four criteria for quality infographics that will help you create and build them in

the learning process. According to them, when creating and developing infographics, you need to take into account the following seven points:

1. Defining goals;
2. Choosing a theme;
3. Balanced integration of text, images, graphics and illustrations must be integrated;
4. Attractiveness, simplicity and clarity in presentation;
5. Balanced combination of Visual Effects, videos, sounds, animations;
6. Authenticity and reliability of the links provided;
7. Compliance and compliance of students with the degree of language proficiency (Nhan & Yen, 2021).

Methods

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design to measure the 8th grade students' current level of working with infographics-based texts of PISA in the section of reading literacy, before implementing intervention to form their media literacy in our further steps of investigation.

Research participants

The study involved 12 students consisting of 7 male and 5 female students from the 8th grade students of N 202 school-gymnasium. They were selected, by the purposive sampling technique, with level from A2 to B1 CEFR levels, since the study requires the participants with an adequate level of English proficiency as infographics-based reading texts in English can hardly be done without an adequate level of English language proficiency (Grabe & Stoller 2011). All of them were Kazakh (L1) native speakers, learning English as a foreign language (L3). The number of the students remained at 12 from the beginning until the end of the experiment.

Research instrument

Zuckerman (2019) identified and described 5 levels of media literacy, describing different activities in the complexity of students' ability to work with the information provided according to each of the media literacy skills in Table 2 below:

Table 1

Media literacy band performance indicators

Bands	Scores %	Skills
Advanced 1	81- 100	Reflect on content and form: Students are able to determine, reflect and evaluate long and detailed information presented in the form of tables, graphs, diagrams, etc.
Proficient 2	61 – 80	Assess quality and interpret questions: Students are able to interpret and integrate a separate piece of information, compare or summarize them.
Basic 3	41-60	Access and retrieve: Students are somewhat able to make a comparison or connection, recognize the features of the text and show clear understanding of the text.
Prerequisite 4	21-40	Integrate and generate inferences: Students are able to understand the clear structure of the visual representation of Information (tables, maps, diagrams, etc.)
Far below basic 5	20 - 0	Represent literal information: finding individual pieces of clearly expressed information on one simple map or line chart, or on a column chart containing small-sized oral text in several words and phrases.

Taking into account the noted levels, the media literacy test with texts were transmitted in the format of infographics in the international testing of PISA:

The 8-item reading proficiency test was written in English and constructed following the PISA reading literacy assessment framework. The test consisted of infographics-based reading passages with 1 question: represent literal information; 1 question: integrate and generate inferences questions; 2 access and retrieve questions; 2 assess quality and interpret questions, and 2 reflect and evaluate questions. The infographics-based reading texts were taken and the questions were adapted from Take the Test, the sample questions from the PISA assessments by OECD, and adjusted to the given media literacy levels in Table 2. The test questions were either in the multiple-choice or written formats. The test was used as the pre-test in order to measure learner's media literacy level and identify the challenges of carrying out the infographics-based tasks before the intervention and the post-test to examine whether and to what extent the students' reading proficiency will be developed in our further research steps after the intervention in a complete version of master's thesis.

The items were tailored to elicit cognitive skills by employing Anderson and Krathwohl's (2001) Revised Bloom's Taxonomy and White's (2011) Text-Task Respondent Theory.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

The data were collected in N 202 school-gymnasium on 9th of December through paper-based testing. Firstly, permissions were secured from the school administrators and teachers involved. During the paper-test session the 12 students worked with four different passages with overall 8 problem tasks individually. The

collected data were analyzed descriptively into percentage count.

Results

Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrate the 8th grade students' current media literacy level and mandatory skills in the reading questionnaire section of PISA in N202 school-gymnasium. The findings of the study presented that 40% of the participants from the given pre-test scored band 3, which actually means that half of the students' media literacy level are basic, followed by 40% of students achieved Band 4, and the percentage of the students who reached Proficient and Far below basic levels showed 10% (see Figure 1). Also, the students who comprised Band 3 and Band 2 scorers possessed basic and prerequisite levels of media literacy in the reading section. It can be seen that Band 3 scores were noticeably from Assylbek (45%), Yerkezhan (47%), Alinur (52%), Aldilkhan (45%), Yesset (60%) and Miras (55%), whereas Band 4 scorers are Imanali (39), Alau (27), Aizere (35) and Kausar (36) (see Figure 2). These students could clearly comprehend the visual representation of the information, however lacked at accessing and retrieving the infographics-based texts. Amongst all the students only Ayanat and Zhanel achieved Band 2 and Band 5, showing the percentages of 75% and 18%, respectively. Overall, absenteeism of participants, who reached Advanced and Proficient levels of Media Literacy, presents that students lack reflecting and evaluating skills, including interpreting, integrating and making comparisons of the given graph-based information.

Research Question 1: What level of media literacy are the 8th grade students on?

Research Question 2: What skills are needed to form the 8th grade students' media literacy?

Figure 1. Distribution in Band Performance in Media Literacy

Figure 2. Total Scores of the students (%)

Discussions

The primary purpose of this research paper is to find out the necessary skills (see Table 1) to work with graph information effectively and investigate current media literacy level of 8th grade students in N 202 school-gymnasium, in order to use the gathered findings in our further investigations of master's thesis. The students generally attained Band 3 (Basic) and Band 4 (prerequisites). At this level, they could identify and recognize simple information to distinguish the main ideas from the infographics-based tasks. Students were somewhat able to exhibit a general understanding of the information but could not draw connections of the given graphs. These students had minimal input in comprehending information from texts and could only make a simple connection in single information. Band 2 scorers were able to integrate information from texts but lacked the ability in forming arguments based on evidence.

Generally, prior studies showed and justified that lack of abilities at interpreting and integrating graph-based texts, reflecting and evaluating them with higher order thinking skills are the main issue and reason why Kazakhstani students have shown lowest results in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). Possible explanation for the result might be the lack of evaluating, reflecting and interpreting skills due to the deficiency of infographics-based reading tasks in students' books and lack of practices due to the curricula of state schools. These factors still have to be explored in future studies.

The findings of this research are consistent with the study of Jane et.al (2020) who found the trends and patterns of Malaysian high schoolers' reading literacy performance. However, the concrete findings of students' low media literacy level have not been previously described in other studies which was the limitation of this research. In future studies, the results obtained in our investigation will contribute to a more

concrete analysis and intervention for forming 8th grade student's media literacy.

Conclusion

The study provides an overview of 8th grade students' media literacy levels in reading performance in PISA. Skill-based reporting offers an overview of students' media literacy skills and level in the reading questionnaire section of PISA. There is a need to train students to become competent readers who can adapt, reflect and evaluate texts critically. These are the essential markers of a competent reader in the 21st century. In short, media literacy is a required skill in order to survive in a global environment. It also works like a compass that promotes students' employability requirement in the workplace and helps in building a culture of innovation. And infographics might lead to a significant increase in students' achievement, therefore teachers should be encouraged to use infographics in foreign language lessons, and students should be encouraged to develop a positive attitude towards the use of infographics in various courses. The takeaway from this study shows that students need to synthesize graph information and evaluate arguments from multiple perspectives that align with deep comprehension. The implication of the findings points out that students require a strong foundation in processing cognitive tasks when it comes to specific skills such as the ability to analyze and evaluate. In a classroom setting, learning and drilling should intensely focus on exposing students to learn activities that primarily emphasize cultivating media literacy skills through using infographics in systematic and developmental ways.

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PUBLICISTIC GENRES IN THE FORMATION OF THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Shnaliyeva S.

Master's student of the "Foreign language teachers' training"

Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages, Kazakhstan

Abstract

As we know, nowadays training in the system of higher professional education in Kazakhstan requires highly qualified specialists. The formation of communicative competence of a future specialist is one of the actual problems in the process of education. This article aims to determine the possible ways of the publicistic genres in the formation of the communicative competence of future teachers. Furthermore, the article delineates the term communicative competence and its methodological aspects, discusses the classification of the publicistic genres, analyze the types of publicistic genres which can help to develop the level of communicative competence of future teachers of foreign language.

Keywords: competence, communicative competence, foreign language, future teachers of foreign languages, publicistic genres.

Introduction

Modern society is developing very dynamically. Integration of Kazakhstan into the world educational space actualizes the development of professional contacts with representatives of foreign countries and puts forward new requirements for graduates. The purpose of higher education is to train specialists with professional, communicative, and foreign language competence, creative potential, and critical thinking style. In this regard, there is a need to transform the educational environment of higher education into a single creatively developing educational space that promotes the formation of communicative competence as a factor of successful self-realization in professional activities. In a broad sense, communicative competence can be interpreted as an ability and readiness to carry out foreign language communication, both interpersonal and intercultural.

Communicative competence is one of the most important qualitative characteristics of an individual, allowing him to realize his needs for social recognition, respect, and self-actualization in the process of socialization. American linguist N. Chomsky was one of the first who introduced this term into scientific usage, by

which he understood "the system of intellectual abilities, the system of knowledge and beliefs that develops in early childhood and interaction with many other factors determines ... types of behavior". Ethnolinguist D. Hymes defined communicative competence as "the creative ability of a person to use the inventory of linguistic means (in the form of statements and discourses), which is composed of knowledge and readiness to use them adequately.

In the literature, scientists, recognizing the importance of one or another component in the professional competence of the teacher, point to the special role of the communicative component. The formation of this component is considered to be an important condition for the development of the professional activity of a teacher and his/her professional competence. Especially in foreign language teaching methodology, the development and formation of students' foreign language communicative competence are considered the main goal of foreign language teaching. The importance of communicative competence is explained not only by the fact that a foreign language is a subject of study (at university) and the subject of teaching (at school), but also by the fact that communicative prop-